

Speakable and unspeakable in gravitation

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Abstract

The reality of space curvature, matter conservation, dark energy, black holes is questioned. The role of long range gravitomagnetism is stressed in relation to the existence of missing mass.

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Space curvature, matter conservation, dark energy, black holes

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1 Introduction

It appears that the present trend of physics is, alas, more of a philological nature, namely of asserting the existence of non existing entities and labelling them with catchy words: missing mass, dark energy, black holes, space warping, down to quintessence and to define a discrepancy a tension and a "dull" tide effect a spaghettification. We have tried to show that all these effects might have a common origin essentially due to an inadequate equation. An extension of Special Relativity (SR) [1] to the treatment of gravitation [2], as confronted with General Relativity (GR) [3] will be presented. The incorrect claim of the reality of space deformation and the unavoidable time dependence of the Newtonian potential will be dealt with and their consequences derived in connection with the presumed dark energy presence. In particular the long range relativistic gravitomagnetic interaction $O(1/r)$ will be shown to provide the necessary contribution overweighting the usual Newtonian $O(1/r^2)$ to dispose of missing mass. A substantial presence of the equally long range gravitational radiation in flat space will be underlined. The present paper represents an overall improved reformulation of previous works [4][5][6].

folklore	reality	comments
space deformation	Euclidean geometry (Painleve-Gullstrand metric)	flat space, non Euclidean geometries are an alternative unnecessary complication
black holes	non existing apart from our Universe	mean life estimate disproves their existence
dark energy	$Mc^2 = GM^2/R$	no cosmological constant no dark energy no acceleration constancy of physical laws causal connection
matter conservation	time dependent age of the Universe	matter non conservation
missing mass or MOND	gravitomagnetism	long range 1/r explains presumed missing mass effects and gravitational lensing
space time ripples for gravitational waves	gravitational radiation in flat space	gravitational radiation not proper to GR

2 Gravitation and the invariant Minkowski interval

The role Special Relativity [1] has played in our understanding of the world can hardly be underestimated. Indeed the passage from the notion of separate space and time to space-time has been a true revolution both on the theoretical and on the practical side.

Its content can be summarized by the introduction of the invariant interval which connects space and time in inertial frames

$$ds^2 = c^2 dt^2 - dr^2 \quad (1)$$

with obvious meaning of the symbols.

Its extension to gravitation, which was classically accounted for by Newton's law [2] via an instantaneous action at a distance, has represented a formidable problem culminating in the famous theory of General Relativity.

However by the EP (Equivalence Principle), the invariant interval has the standard Minkowski form in EPIFs (Equivalence Principle Inertial Frames), in which the ordinary inertial frame law holds and light propagates isotropically and always with velocity c , to first order in space-time displacements :

Thus the local validity of the principles of SR implies that ds^2 is still given by the same expression, Eq.(1), in the coordinates employed by any observer around the given space-time point, to the first order, independently of his motion. All the SR results hold therefore locally, for all observers (on arbitrary trajectories) to first order in the coordinates defined by their clocks and rods, with the Minkowski interval given by the ordinary expression.

The above observation allows to write the Minkowski intervals, all of the same form in their EPIF variables around different points, in global coordinates:

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &= c^2 dt^2 - (dr - v(r) dt)^2 - dx_{\perp}^2 = \\ &= c^2(1 - v^2(r)/c^2) dt^2 + 2v(r) dt dr - dr^2 - dx_{\perp}^2 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Eq.(2) gives nothing else than the Painlevé [7]-Gullstrand [8] metric (P-G), a solution of the GR equations in a central field, obtained here (as a solution of no whatsoever equation other than Newton's law) on the pure basis of Euclidean space and absolute "free fall" time. The consideration of the radial part $dr^2(dt=0)$ confirms its Euclidean nature.

Thus [9] [10]

$$GR = SR + Newton + equivalence principle$$

Even if built on Euclidean space and absolute time, it represents nevertheless a non-Minkowskian space-time, due to the crossed term. Nevertheless P-G reproduces at the same time the so called "three crucial tests" of GR.

Clearly, in this approach, SR enters at a different stage with respect to the description of radial free fall. The latter is given by the Newton free fall velocity in global coordinates; the velocity of light enters in the local relativistic structure of space time, which is trivial in EPIFs and globally determined by Eqs.(2).

All gravitational effects depend on the "weak field" parameter

$$\epsilon(r) \equiv 2GM/rc^2 = v^2(r)/c^2 \quad (3)$$

The usual (Schwarzschild [11]) catchy picture of a funnel-like space deformation (which seems to suggest an inevitable fall of all objects towards the source, Fig.2)

next paragraph) is replaced by the standard familiar one i.e. the distance between two concentric spheres is simply the Euclidean one Fig.1).

Thus **geodetics are the "traditional" free fall one.**

Figure 1: In the P-G metric the distance between two concentric spheres is simply the Euclidean one. Thus no space deformation results. The two dimensional example, contrasting Feynman's picture [12], is trivially translated to the three dimensional case.

The "reality" of space deformation (non Euclidean geometries) is contradicted by the very existence of different "equivalent" metrics.

The photon radial velocity reads

$$dr/dt = \pm c - v(r) \quad (4)$$

It embodies obviously the equivalence principle which is at the base of GR. ¹

GR is said to treat satisfactorily the strong field case. However **GR represents in reality a low energy treatment of gravitation.**

This statement is confirmed by comparing the (massive) free fall law (or escape velocity)

$$v^2(r) - 2\frac{GM}{r} = 0 \quad (5)$$

with the one for photons

$$\hbar\omega(1 - \frac{GM}{c^2r}) = \hbar\omega' \quad (6)$$

and observing that photons cannot escape ($\omega' = 0$) for $\frac{GM}{c^2\bar{R}} = 1$, henceforth \bar{R} standing for the BH radius both in the traditional Schwarzschild formulation and therefore with a factor of 2 in the previous definition, or in the correct one for photons.

The application of the simple energy conservation law for photons, confirmed at the lowest level, yields in the general case the same red shift relation of GR apart from

¹An interesting historical reconstruction can be found in [13]. The contribution of Painleve' can be appreciated not only for the mathematics ("in the invariant GR interval two **arbitrary** functions of r appear with quite general requirements") but also for having introduced in Newtonian physics the notion of proper time. Indeed the apparent puzzling coexistence of different metrics can be traced to the fact there is an infinity of r solutions meeting the Einstein conditions. Thus GR does not uniquely determine the invariant interval and in that sense the above physical requirement of the P-G one puts it on a privileged status. In conclusion the implementation of Newton's law in the invariant Minkovski interval simply realizes the GR program.

undetectable second order terms. And this statement is backed up by Einstein himself who gave also a different proof (energy conservation) for the red shift prediction.

Thus of the so called three crucial tests of GR only light deflection and Mercury perihelion precession remains. As regards the former (accounted for already by Newtonian dynamics just as a consequence of Special Relativity, although with a wrong factor of two), it has been shown by Feynman [14] that this factor can be straightforwardly obtained just by using the spin 2 graviton interaction; in that sense it might be regarded as a proof of the existence of gravitons rather than of space time deformation. In addition it might be curious to regard part of the effect obtainable in Euclidean geometry and the rest (factor 2) as a proof of space deformation.

Thus all these effects confirm the GR treatment at $O(\epsilon) \ll 1$. The validity of its extension to the strong field case and especially to BHs where $\epsilon = 1$ remains totally open.

Let us conclude with some obvious remarks. SR is valid when gravitation is irrelevant i.e. typically for strong interaction distances. Any inclusion of a gravitational corrective term "deforms" space- time but leaves open the separate effects on space and time (different metrics). This deformation is just a tool for implementing in a causal structure the additional interaction without more physical significance more than deforming absolute space and time in SR.

3 The Schwarzschild solution

The Schwarzschild [11] solution of GR is given by

$$ds'^2 = c^2(1 - v^2(r)/c^2) dt^2 - dr^2/(1 - v^2/c^2) - dx_{\perp}^2 \quad (7)$$

the prime referring to Ss.

The previous expression is popular because of the similarity with the corresponding one in SR, where space and time variables have a direct link with reality.

The photon radial velocity reads

$$dr/dt = \pm c(1 - v^2(r)/c^2) \quad (8)$$

As well known a singularity at the Ss radius only arises in this metric as a consequence of its unphysicality. The same thing happens for the "warping" in the case of radiation, where a similar unfortunate choice of the metric convinced Einstein of the non existence of gravitational waves [16].

In the P-G metric the Ss singularity does not exist and the two have been shown to be connected by a time transformation which however obscures the Euclidean nature of the first one.

Figure 2: Space time gravitational deformation [15] to which, because of the separate treatment of space and time coordinates corresponds an analogous deformation in space coordinates in the Ss metric. Indeed the distance between concentric spheres of areas $4\pi r^2$ and $4\pi(r+dr)^2$ is $\sqrt{\frac{1}{1-2GM/r}}dr > dr$ i.e greater than the same in Euclidean space.

4 Spooky black holes

The black hole lifetime can be obtained in two alternative ways. The first is

$$t = \frac{R}{c} \quad (9)$$

i.e. the standard way the approximate age of the Universe is evaluated (a more realistic could be derived from Fig.6). It can be derived also from the expression, which to the best of our knowledge has not been considered so far, from which an interesting result emerges, namely the Universe dependence on its mass content

$$t' = \frac{GM}{c^3} \quad (10)$$

Thus a shorter age in the past should have been accompanied by a smaller mass (as well as a smaller radius). This shows that matter is not conserved [17].

A less qualitative argument applies. Consider the free fall time from infinity under the Newtonian potential. Then

$$\frac{dr}{dt} = \sqrt{\frac{2GM}{r}} \quad (11)$$

The time T is given by

$$T = 2/3\sqrt{\frac{R^3}{2GM}} \quad (12)$$

where R stands for the radius of the source. This applies of course to any gravitational object and specifically to the BH case, where by use of the BH relation

$$T_{BH} = 4/3 \frac{GM}{c^3} \quad (13)$$

Of course only for BHs M and R are connected so that the free fall time in absolute time is alternatively $T \simeq \bar{R}/c$. The result has an immediate interpretation and confirms the dimensional result of [17] of the mean life of a black hole. **The above free fall time (and equally escape time) is a mean life measure since it applies also when the escaping particle is a part of the object at its surface.** It should be once more emphasized that all is based just on the Newtonian potential which is the only physical ingredient of the P-G metric and hence of GR.

If $t = t'$ (of course at this level the factor 2 is irrelevant) the object is a black hole, which is not the case for those reported in [18]. Let us underline that this result does not come from the consideration of unknown dynamics at these extreme conditions but only from general arguments.

The relevant point is, however, not so much that they do not fulfill the black hole requirement but that **even in the most favorable cases the estimated lifetime is a fraction of a year**, irrelevant at cosmological scales. *Thus BHs should exist but cannot be seen: very reminiscent of dark energy!* This renders all related speculations [19], [20] just academic in the sense that since black holes do not exist it is obvious that quantum evaporation and the accompanying loss of information are just a beautiful mathematical exercise.

5 Cosmological extension. The time dependent Newton potential

Fundamental cosmological information has come from the Hubble parameter whose present value H_0 can be used to determine the approximate age of the Universe (for a more quantitative one see Fig.6), since $[1/H_0] = [t]$. It can be connected to the dimension R of the visible Universe and the light velocity c as

$$t_U = \frac{1}{H_0} = \frac{R}{c}$$

Numerically, with the value $R \simeq 10^{26}$ it yields

$$t_U \simeq .3 \times 10^{18}$$

This is a qualitative argument (almost) nobody would object to.

There is however another quantity with the same dimensions

$$t'_U = \frac{GM}{c^3}$$

which has however stunning and unquestionable consequences. It yields the same result for $M = Nm_N$, where m_N stands for the nucleon mass and $N \simeq 10^{80}$ for the nucleon number. These two figures are taken from [21].

The two values coincide as they should. In that case one immediately obtains

$$t_U = \frac{R}{c} = t'_U = \frac{GM}{c^3}$$

i. e.

$$\epsilon = \frac{GM}{c^2 R} = 1$$

”the well known BH condition” which supports the suggestion by Feynman [14]. The preceding equation embodies the ”striking relation between the age of the Universe and its mass content.” Now tautologically in the past the age must have been smaller and this implies that the (visible) mass must have been less or in other words **”that there has been matter creation”**. Restraining for simplicity to the matter dominated regime starting at $R \simeq 10^{23}m$, a constant mass would imply a constant age and we would have the situation represented in Fig.3) i.e. *a discrepancy by three orders of magnitude*.

Figure 3: Universe age in matter conserving GR (dashed curve) and in matter non conserving present approach (continuous red curve). Time in seconds and mass in terms of the nucleon number N. The inadequacy of the former is evident.

Therefore the GR fundamental assumption of nucleon number conservation has to be disposed of and **GR has no predictive power for the future and does not reproduce the past of the Universe**. This is no surprise since GR was formulated

within the theoretical scenario of a static Universe where already the "repulsive agent" represented a problem. Were the epigones who unduly forced its extension to an expanding Universe. The problem of the non detectability of such an effect has been considered in [22].

Figure 4: Train (only?) cemetery near Uyuni (Bolivia).

Unthinking respect for authority is the greatest enemy of truth A.Einstein

The description of the Universe evolution as a gigantic and evolving black hole, has encountered many objections. In particular how has it been possible the development to the present unconventional one with a big mass in a large volume obeying however the same relation $M/R = c^2/G$ of a conventional tiny and very dense i.e. the Planck (P) one, where gravitation and Q.M. successfully combine. (see final section). For Planck quantities the same relation which holds for the Universe is valid i.e.

$$t_P = \frac{GM_P}{c^3} \tag{14}$$

which strongly suggests a continuous expansion of such an object.

In fact this condition which essentially corresponds to energy conservation does not correspond to a minimum in energy. Indeed if we allow a perturbation in R at the Planck era

$$R \rightarrow R + dR$$

we cannot have shrinking with a radius smaller than the Planck one and a bigger one naturally entails a correspondingly increase in the mass. The same argument also holds true also for later times even if a smaller radius cannot be discarded in principle. However the same observation remains valid : no restoring force! Consider indeed the radiation dominated era where the mass is given by

$$M \simeq (kT)^4 R^3.$$

Of course in principle both possibilities exist i.e. increase and decrease in R with constant $M/R \simeq (kT)^4 R^2$. In the first case M/R remains constant at the price of a decreasing temperature $(KT)^2 \simeq 1/R$ which is what is actually observed. In the second case the opposite should happen in contrast to reality. The possibility of perturbing to a smaller radius (at constant mass) would result in energy violation since the negative self energy would overcompensate the mass. In other words again only a bigger radius is

possible (smaller self energy) and mass creation is demanded to restore energy balance. In the case of the matter dominated era even if photons are a very small fraction of nucleons the above argument holds true. A contraction would decrease the photon wavelength (anti CMB) and this implies that also for nucleons expansion is the only possibility. Thus the particle mass content simply increases. Expansion in the radiation dominated era would correspond, loosely speaking, to the Boltzmann thermal death whereas in the matter dominated era, where nucleons are non relativistic, the negative heat capacity would allow the birth of new structures.

As mentioned, the treatment of the Newton potential enters in the connection between the self energy and the mass which implies (following Feynman's conjecture [14]) that the energy to assemble from infinity many masses $M = \sum_i m(i)$ is zero when their self energy provides a deep enough potential well

$$Mc^2 - \frac{GM^2}{R} = 0 \quad (15)$$

Notice that this equation predicts a BH radius, in line with our previous considerations about photons, at variance by a factor 2 with respect to the traditional one. The above requirement is easily understood. A bound gravitational system of whichever form (photons or matter) increases its energy when the interaction distance increases. Since energy must be conserved this can happen only by allowing for matter (energy) creation to restore the energy balance. Of course this approach is highly speculative but "we must remember that here we are not dealing with an ordinary problem but with a cosmological problem" [14]. It is obviously based on the form of the Newtonian potential, probed in familiar contexts, implemented by the BH condition.

This implies

$$\epsilon = \frac{GM}{c^2 R} = 1 \quad (16)$$

Indeed for the present Universe

$$\frac{GM_U}{c^2 R_U} \simeq 1$$

It is obvious that in a Universe which would expanded to a radius R'_U , if the mass would have remained constant, as in the standard GR treatment where $\rho = 1/R^3$, the previous value would have become

$$\epsilon' = \frac{GM_U}{c^2 R'_U} = \epsilon \times \frac{R_U}{R'_U} \quad (17)$$

i.e the same effect considered before ! To cure it we must admit that the total mass has varied , necessarily increasing by the same amount. ²

This reflects in the **constancy of the strong field parameter** ϵ . ³ Thus

$$\frac{d\epsilon}{dt} = 0 \quad \textit{acceleration equation} \quad (18a))$$

²Such a relation which realizes Mach's principle has also been used by [23] in considering the possibility of a G variation. This however has been experimentally disproved.

³It has been strongly emphasized [24] how close to the critical one the density in the course of the expansion must have been otherwise we would not be here.

Indeed *the constancy of ϵ implies the cancellation of the acceleration*. **In an expanding Universe the potential is not a state function so that in its derivative an extra term due to the mass variation appears in addition to the standard Newtonian acceleration:**

$$\frac{d\epsilon}{dt} = \frac{GdM}{Rdt} - \frac{GMdR}{R^2dt} = \frac{GdM}{RdR} \frac{dR}{dt} - \frac{GMdR}{R^2dt} = 0 \quad (19)$$

where the last term is proportional to the acceleration

$$a = \frac{GM}{R^2}$$

cancelled by the mass variation

$$\frac{GdM}{RdR}$$

Let us slightly transform the BH equation. Consider a spherical ball of given matter density and a mass m at its surface, whose motion is determined only by the matter inside. The dimensions of the ball disappear since H enters as $c^2 \simeq H^2 R^2 \simeq G\rho' R^2$ thus implementing **homogeneity** (and isotropy). It can be rewritten as

$$\frac{c^2}{R^2} = H^2 = G\rho' \quad \text{energy equation} \quad (18b)$$

where $\rho' = 4/3\pi\rho$. **It is stunningly similar but profoundly different from Friedman's equation.** It also assumes Euclidean space in line with the treatment of gravitation at a local level.

Thus

$$\frac{dM}{M} = \frac{dR}{R} = \frac{d\chi}{\chi} \quad (20)$$

χ being the scale factor (traditionally denoted by the confusing R). Eq.(18b) "the energy equation" and Eq. (18a) "the acceleration equation" thus form the basis of our treatment.

The interesting results of the **BH equations are: no cosmological constant since the energy equation is homogeneous and therefore no dark energy, the repulsive term coming from the counterterm in the no acceleration equation.**

An additional argument why ϵ cannot depend on time is that the only reasonable possibility is

$$\frac{d\epsilon}{dt} \simeq H(t)\epsilon$$

Now since H is positive and $\epsilon(\text{Planck}) = \epsilon(U) = 1$, as it will be shown later, this eventuality is discarded.

As regards the presumed acceleration, the Universe would be decelerating for $R \simeq t^{2/3}$ and hence light would take less time to reach us from distant stars; therefore distant objects would look brighter. Thus in order to justify their apparent faintness one had to invoke an acceleration. On the contrary in the present approach, since expansion was a steady one, high z (the redshift parameter) objects are actually farther apart than in the traditional scenario and hence fainter. We then see that the time evolution

predicted by GR can only be maintained at the price of introducing ad hoc parameters, which disappear in the present description. One might object that one has replaced one parameter with another one. This is however not completely true in the sense that our "creation" mechanism has some microscopic justification, and is predictive without further adjustments, in addition to accounting for causality whereas dark energy and inflation seem just questionable recipes.

In the evaluation of the time dependence of the density ρ , appearing in $\rho\chi^2$ if matters is conserved i.e.

$$dM/dt = d/dt(\chi^3\rho(t)) = 3\rho\chi^2d\chi/dt + \chi^3d\rho/dt \quad (21)$$

which yields the familiar density dependence

$$d\rho/\rho = -3d\chi/\chi \quad (22)$$

(and the analogous one for photons) proper to General Relativity, one obtains the standard Newtonian like relation

$$\frac{\ddot{\chi}}{\chi} = -G\rho \quad (23)$$

If on the other hand for the linear relation between radius and mass $dM/M = d\chi/\chi$ one has the equally homogeneous

$$d\rho/\rho = -2d\chi/\chi \quad (24)$$

and

$$\ddot{\chi} = 0 \quad (25)$$

$$\dot{\chi} = c \quad (26)$$

Thus the counterterm in the acceleration replaces here the cosmological constant at present. Its value should be of the same order of magnitude of the vacuum (v) density

$$\rho_v \simeq \frac{M}{R^3} \simeq 10^{-25} \quad (27)$$

to be compared to the same quantity at Planck times

$$\rho_v^P \simeq 10^{97} \quad (28)$$

with the notorious ratio of $\simeq 10^{120}$ [25]. Of course at earlier times we would have different "cosmological constants".

In the BH model there is no critical density. The given one is just of the right amount predicted by the model. It must have evolved from the Planck era to the present one determining the curvature radius R_C ($1/R_C^2 \simeq G\rho/c^2$) i.e. a Universe in the matter era essentially flat. A totally different scenario than the GR one. This also determines the fate of the Universe : no big crunch, nor big bounce but a density decrease which might anyway foresee the possibility of more diluted structure formation due to the negative heat capacity of gravitation.

Figure 5: The Universe evolution. The lines $R = ct$ represent the borders of **the causally connected expanding Universe**. A different history than presently proposed is evident. First, inflation which was invoked to account for homogeneity (with problems of causality) is not needed. Also the recent time development which seems to present peculiar features : a deceleration (due to gravitational attraction) followed by a later acceleration phase, does not show up in the present approach.

Let us finally consider a more sophisticated model, i.e. the description of a homogeneous isotropic expanding Universe given by the local invariant interval in the Lemaitre-Hubble-Painleve-Gullstrand metric

$$c^2 = c^2 dt^2 - \chi^2(t) dx^2 \quad (29)$$

$y = \chi x$ and the Hubble parameter $H = H(t) = \frac{\dot{\chi}}{\chi}$.

Thus $ds^2 = c^2 dt^2 - \chi^2(t) \left[\left(\frac{dy}{\chi} - \frac{\dot{\chi}}{\chi^2} y dt \right)^2 \right]$

or

$$ds^2 = dt^2 (c^2 - (\dot{y} - Hy)^2) \quad (30)$$

So the original space part of the invariant interval has been transformed in a velocity dependent one.

Here $Hy = v(t, y)$ represents the velocity of expansion of the point y at the time t and light propagation results as shown in Fig. 6).

This coordinate system based on a cosmological extension of the Painleve-Gullstrand coordinates shows in addition that the proper time of relativistically receding galaxies

is of course longer than ours. Thus they are shown to live longer than naively expected. In both formulations the Universe is causally connected.

Figure 6: Universe expansion in the Painlevé - Gullstrand- Lemaitre- Hubble metric. It implements the cosmological equivalence principle and is causally connected.

6 Long range gravitational forces

a) Gravitomagnetism and missing mass

The Newtonian treatment of gravitation for bound systems, slightly rearranged reads

$$v^2 r = GM \tag{31}$$

If the asymptotic value of v (i.e. where the Keplerian law $v \simeq 1/r$ loses its validity) remains constant that implies

$$M \simeq r$$

i.e.

$$\rho(r) \simeq 1/r^2 \quad (32)$$

This observation has led to many speculations : modification of the equation of motion (Milgrom's MOND [26]) and the seemingly alternative missing mass hypothesis with the accompanying theoretical speculations about MACHOs and the like.

We are here in the presence of an effect which cannot be accounted for by GR relativistic corrections $O(v^2/c^2) \simeq 10^{-6}$ to Newton's law just from inspection.

To start with, a straightforward manipulation of Milgrom's equation with the simple interpolating function $\mu(a/a_0) = 1/1 + a_0/a$ correcting the Newtonian acceleration in terms of a new "fundamental" constant a_0 , yields

$$\frac{GM(1 + a_0/a)}{r^2} = a \quad (33)$$

which can immediately interpreted as an ordinary Newton equation with standard $a = v^2/r$ but with an increased mass $M = M(1 + a_0/a)$ where the extra term may be interpreted as "dark matter" (DM) or missing mass. **Thus MOND and missing mass are just two alternative equivalents fits, both destitute of any physical foundation.**

In addition this does justice to the speculations about seasonal variations of dark matter. Indeed it would be hard to believe in a seasonal variation of (corrections to) Newton's law. The DM amount "predicted by MOND" is anyhow constrained by the acceleration and does not show up as a totally arbitrary parameter.

A more physical approach is provided [27] by considering the role of gravitomagnetism whose presence is confirmed by gravitational lensing experiments [28] and by **the prediction of the Coriolis force.** The dimensions of the gravitomagnetic field h entering the Lorentz Heaviside force

$$\mathbf{F} = m(\mathbf{g} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{h}) \quad (34)$$

are

$$[h] = [T^{-1}] \simeq \omega$$

i.e. a gravitomagnetic field is dimensionally equivalent to an angular velocity, the proportionality coefficient depending of course on the geometry. However one can get the form of gravitomagnetism just from dimensional arguments. First of all it must be an $1/c^2$ effect. Second it must contain the factor GM which to make the coefficient in front of the term h adimensional enters in the form $\frac{GM}{c^2 r}$.

This makes gravitomagnetism a long range $1/r$ effect, as opposed to the usual $1/r^2$ Newtonian term and suggests it might account for the density dependence outlined above.

The basic equation has hence to be regarded

$$\frac{v^2}{r} = \frac{GM}{r^2} + 2hv \quad (35)$$

where the first term represents the Newtonian contribution which yields the Keplerian orbiting velocities and the last one of the r.h.s. is due to the gravitomagnetic field

h of the core rotating with angular velocity ω_G (G= galaxy). This term has the form of a Coriolis force, which appears in non inertial frames, increasing the tangential velocity in the rotating frame and results in a total velocity in the external inertial frame (we on earth in a first approximation) given by this velocity plus the velocity of rotation (as measured from the Doppler shift of H21 lines in the orbital plane).

As mentioned the gravitomagnetic force is proportional to the angular velocity as

$$h = \epsilon_G \omega_G \quad (36)$$

where the coefficient ϵ_G is

$$\epsilon_G \simeq \frac{GM_G}{c^2 r} \quad (37)$$

A very simple evaluation of the gravitomagnetic term alone would yield

$$\bar{v} \simeq \frac{GM_G}{c^2} \omega_G$$

where the term of the r.h.s. in fraction, with the given numerical values of M33, yields 10^{13} to be compared to the term on the l.h.s. of 10^5 . Thus an ω_G of the order of 10^{-8} , which means a rotation period of the core of some years, would do the job. So the core would indeed rotate, as conjectured with a greater velocity than the outskirts. Of course this hypothesised core angular velocity has nothing to do with the angular velocity of orbiting objects which only can be read off from the data. It is worth noticing that in the previous equation the factor $GM_G/c^2 r_C$ of the core enters, very reminiscent of a black hole.

A plot of v for the values $v = 10^5 m/s, r = 10^{20} m$ and $M_G \simeq 10^{11} M_S (S = sun) \simeq 10^{40} kg$ is reported in the Fig. 7).

Figure 7: Rotation curve of the galaxy M33. The inner part is obtained by assuming that the core has a uniform mass density with $M_G \simeq 10^{11} M_S$. The yellow curve represents the Newtonian $v \simeq \sqrt{1}/r$ and the green curve with the additional effect of gravitomagnetism. In the vertical axis units of v in $10^5 m/s$ and in the horizontal axis of r in $10^{20} m$. The horizontal red line the MOND fit with $v^4 \simeq M$.

Of course this treatment is admittedly and necessarily approximate in the sense that the core does not rotate all at the same angular velocity. It is also straightforward to get for the centripetal gravitomagnetic acceleration

$$2hv \simeq 2h^2r \simeq 10^{-10}m/s^2$$

i.e. obviously the same value demanded by MOND.

It is also immediate to see the absence of this gravitomagnetic effect on the earth motion due to the Sun rotation.

Thus the gravitomagnetic force, adding to the usual Newtonian one "in non inertial frames", provides the extra attraction which increases the velocities and in a Newtonian context had to be attributed either to a bigger mass than that responsible for the luminosity or a modification of Newton's law. The relation to frame dragging and geodetic precession has been discussed elsewhere [4]. Although the presence of gravitomagnetism in unquestionable the angular velocity of the core, even if reasonable, enters as a (measurable?) parameter.

b) Gravitational radiation

The first indirect evidence of gravitational radiation has come from the observation of the energy loss of the binary pulsars (PSR B1913+16 [29] and PSR J0737-3039A/B [30]). This has been considered to be a crucial test of Einstein's GR and has strengthened the general belief of space-time curved by matter and of gravitational waves as "ripples which propagate in space time" or "warping of space time"!

On the contrary it has been shown [31] that such an effect just comes from special relativity and that its prediction leads to an alternative simpler interpretation of physical reality. Indeed an analogous set of "Heaviside" vector has been derived to $O(v^2/c^2)$ just from special relativity.

In this connection it has long been noticed the striking similarity between the expression for the electromagnetic quadrupole radiation

$$W_{el} = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{180c^5} \left(\frac{d^3Q}{dt^3} \right)^2 \quad (38)$$

and the gravitational one

$$W_G = \frac{G}{45c^5} \left(\frac{d^3Q}{dt^3} \right)^2 \quad (39)$$

Q representing respectively the electric and gravitational quadrupole, the essential feature being played by the relativistic mass current density which differs from the e.m. one by a factor of 2.

Thus the gravitational radiation can be obtained from the e.m. one in elementary terms ($2^2 \rightarrow 4$) and ($G \rightarrow 1/(4\pi\epsilon_0)$).

Additional evidence comes from the consideration of linear inertial forces, where radiation and Mach's principle combine to confirm (once more) the equality of inertial and gravitational masses

$$m_{in} = \frac{GM_U}{c^2 R_U} m_{grav}$$

7 Gravitation and QM

It is often said that gravitation and QM (quantum mechanics) cannot be treated satisfactorily at the same time. If that means that QM and GR space distortion cannot be reconciled the previous discussion proves that spacial distortion has no physical foundation. Apart from that let us start with the well known QM remedy of the classical atomic infrared catastrophe i.e. the uncertainty principle which gives for the atomic Bohr radius

$$a_o = \frac{ke^2}{\hbar m_e}$$

By the same tools one gets the gravitational Bohr radius

$$a(G)_o = \frac{\hbar^2}{Gm_e^2 M_n}$$

whose value is of the same order of the present estimated radius of the Universe. One therefore easily concludes that quantization is irrelevant in the treatment of gravitation at Universe scales. Let us pass to ordinary scales and to the gravitational **neutron interference experiment** [32]

Figure 8: Quantum gravitational neutron interference

which is totally equivalent to the double slit interference of light. Therefore the macroscopical description of gravitation and QM coexist; in addition this experiment proves that at the quantum level gravitation is not just a geometrical effect since the interference fringes depend on

$$\frac{g}{\hbar^2}$$

Consider then the **Planck black hole** [33], where the **Compton wavelength** λ_C of a particle is required to coincide with its BH radius, thus successfully combining gravitation with QM

$$\frac{\hbar}{Mc} = \lambda_C = R_S = \frac{GM}{c^2} \quad (40)$$

It is again the uncertainty principle which at these scales prevents the gravitation singularity and the standard treatment of gravitation is totally inadequate. Thus the Planck mass corresponds to the energy contained in the minimum quantum radius (because it cannot be of smaller dimensions without violating the uncertainty principle) i.e. to **the smallest quantum black hole**.

At these scales we are in the presence of strong interaction effects since

$$E_P R_P \simeq \hbar c \simeq 1$$

and all interactions unify. The Planck charge is [34]

$$q_P \simeq 11.7 e \quad (41)$$

where e stands for the electric charge $\simeq 1.6 \times 10^{-19} C$ and this result might seem to contradict the previous statement. But instead of sweeping remarks [34] like "comparing masses and charges is like comparing apples with oranges" it would not be a demanding task simply to square the above equation obtaining [35]

$$\alpha_P = q_P^2 / 4\pi\epsilon_0 = 137 \alpha = 1 \quad (42)$$

Thus the previous result confirms that " the fine structure constant at Planck scales is indeed unity " implying that gravitation and electromagnetism are equal and strong (see Fig.9) . Analogous results also for the weak and strong coupling constants [35] and the statement "that at the Planck length scale it has been theorized that all the fundamental forces are unified but the exact mechanism of this unification remains unknown" is here countered.

Needless to say the above results, as well as the description of a black hole, depend on the assumption of the validity of the Coulomb and Newton equations. This is anyhow in line with the theoretical instruments used in the derivation of Planck units.

8 Conclusions

In conclusion the aim of the present work has been to show that the present gravitational description of our Universe can be simply derived by the mass variation of the Newton potential

$$GM/R$$

We can conclude with Feynman's [14] remark about GR that "many people have become so hypnotised by the beauty of one side of the equation that they ignore the other, and hence have no physics to investigate".

Figure 9: Time and temperature dependence of the different interactions. Not in scale. This shows how from the present very different values, the coupling constants tend to one at the Planck origin of space-time.

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